

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Implementation of good agricultural practices for sustainable weed management

SPOKE 6 - PRIMARY AGROINDUSTRY

Flagship Project VINO

DELIVERABLE D5.7

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, and demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report describes the guidelines for the management, prevention, and containment of herbicide resistance.

This report is addressed to all those working in the agronomic field and, specifically, to those dealing with herbicide resistance phenomena, providing them with useful tools for managing this phytosanitary threat.

The following Guidelines describe the current legislation concerning plant protection products, the criteria for herbicide classification, and the resistance phenomena known to date, including those linked to miRNA-mediated (epigenetic) regulations that have been investigated within the Flagship Project VINO.

Furthermore, certain factors related to the development of herbicide resistance are identified, and several useful actions for reducing the incidence of resistance are proposed.

The mitigation actions described here are derived from the results of analyses carried out within the Flagship Project VINO.

A) Introduction

Current European legislation about pesticides and plant protection products

The use of plant protection products is regulated at both international and national levels.

On July 15th, 1991, the European Parliament and Council issued Directive 91/414/EEC concerning the placing of plant protection products on the market. This Directive regulated the authorization, marketing, use, and control of plant protection products in commercial form, as well as the active substances used to protect plants from harmful organisms within the European Community. Member States required that plant protection products cannot be placed on the market or used in their territory unless they have authorized the product under this Directive, and they ensured that a plant protection product was not authorized unless its active substances were listed in Annex I and all conditions set therein were fulfilled.

On December 18th, 2006, the European Parliament and Council issued Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals (also called the R.E.A.CH. Regulation), introducing for the first time a globally harmonized system (GHS) for categorizing the hazard and handling requirements for chemicals in the EU. Furthermore, R.E.A.CH. Regulation also established the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), aimed to ensuring a high level of protection of human health and the environment from harmful substances, as well as assessing the safety of chemical substances used within the EU.

On December 16th, 2008, the European Parliament and Council issued Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on the classification, labeling, and packaging of substances and mixtures, also which amended and repealed Directives 67/548/EEC and 1999/45/EC and the Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006. This Regulation harmonized the criteria for the classification of substances and mixtures, as well as the rules on labeling and packaging of hazardous substances and mixtures. It also aims to establish an inventory of classification and labeling of substances.

On October 21st, 2009, the European Parliament and Council issued Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009, which repealed Council Directives 79/117/EEC and 91/414/EEC. This regulation set down rules for the authorization of plant protection products in commercial form and for their placing on the market, use, and control within the EU. It also establishes rules for the approval of active substances, adjuvants, co-formulants, safeners, and synergists that plant protection products contain or consist of. The aim of these provisions is to ensure a high level of protection of human and animal health and the environment, while improving the functioning of the internal market through the harmonization of rules on the placing on the market of plant protection products,

and at the same time enhancing agricultural production. The regulation refers to the precautionary principle to ensure that active substances or products placed on the market do not adversely affect human or animal health or the environment. Member States are not prevented from applying the precautionary principle in cases of scientific uncertainty regarding the risks to human or animal health or the environment posed by plant protection products to be authorized in their territory.

On October 21st, 2009, the European Parliament and Council also issued Directive (EC) 128/2009, which establishes a framework to achieve the sustainable use of pesticides by reducing the risks and impacts of pesticide use on human health and the environment, and by promoting integrated pest management and alternative approaches or techniques, such as non-chemical alternatives to pesticides. The directive applies to pesticides that are plant protection products as defined in Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009.

The issue of herbicide resistance prevention is addressed in Directive (EC) 128/2009, Annex III “General principles of integrated pest management”, which highlights the importance of counteracting this phytosanitary threat. Specifically, Point 6 states that “the professional user should keep the use of pesticides and other forms of intervention to levels that are necessary, e.g. by reduced doses, reduced application frequency or partial applications, considering that the level of risk in vegetation is acceptable and they do not increase the risk for development of resistance in populations of harmful organisms”. Furthermore, Point 7 establishes that “where the risk of resistance against a plant protection measure is known and where the level of harmful organisms requires repeated application of pesticides to the crops, available anti-resistance strategies should be applied to maintain the effectiveness of the products. This may include the use of multiple pesticides with different modes of action”.

Current Italian legislation about pesticides and plant protection products

In Italy, plant protection products must be authorized by the Ministry of Health before being placed on the market and used, for example, in the agricultural sector, in accordance with Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009.

On August 14th, 2012, Directive 2009/128/EC was transposed into national law through Legislative Decree No. 150 – Implementation of Directive 2009/128/EC establishing a framework for Community action to achieve the sustainable use of pesticides. This decree provided the legal basis for the adoption of the National Action Plan (NAP) for the sustainable use of plant protection products.

On January 22nd, 2014, Italy adopted the NAP through the Interministerial Decree – Adoption of the NAP for the sustainable use of plant protection products, pursuant to Article 6 of Legislative Decree No. 150 of August 14th, 2012. The NAP is periodically updated in accordance with the same

legislative decree. On January 22nd, 2014, the final version of the NAP was adopted by decree of the Ministry of Agricultural, Food and Forestry Policies (MIPAAF).

The general objectives of the NAP are:

1. To reduce the risks and impacts of plant protection products on human health and the environment;
2. To promote the implementation of integrated pest management, organic farming, and other alternative approaches;
3. To protect users of plant protection products;
4. To safeguard consumers;
5. To protect aquatic environments and drinking water;
6. To conserve biodiversity and protect ecosystems.

On March 6th, 2015, the Regional Council of Lombardy approved the first edition of the Guidelines for the implementation in Lombardy of the NAP for the sustainable use of plant protection products (Dgr No. X/3233). These regional guidelines were subsequently incorporated and updated through the adoption of Dgr No. 1376/2019 and Dgr No. 5836/2021.

HRAC herbicides classification

Herbicides can be classified in different ways. One classification is based on the timing of application, namely pre-emergence or post-emergence of the crop. Herbicides applied in pre-emergence can be effective against grasses or broadleaves, while those applied in post-emergence can be either selective (target-specific) or non-selective (broad-spectrum).

Another classification is based on their mode or mechanism of action (MoA), defined as the type of physiological alteration (biochemical or biophysical) through which the herbicide exerts its phytotoxic effect on the treated plant. The modes of action include:

1. lipid biosynthesis inhibitors;
2. amino acid biosynthesis inhibitors;
3. plant growth regulators;
4. photosynthesis inhibitors;
5. nitrogen metabolism inhibitors;
6. pigment inhibitors;
7. cell membrane disruptors;
8. seedling growth inhibitors.

pyrimidinyl benzoates, sulfonyleureas, and imidazolinones are different herbicide molecules that act as acetolactate synthase inhibitors.

The MoA of herbicides is essential for understanding their management, classification, organization, and hierarchy. It also provides an overview of herbicide resistance, which continues to pose a major challenge for sustainable agricultural management.

Excessive and repeated use of the same herbicide formulations has led to an increase in the development of resistance phenomena among weeds, causing significant damage to plants of agricultural and landscape value. Managing the occurrence of herbicide resistance represents a major challenge in achieving sustainable and efficient agriculture.

Herbicide resistance

Herbicide resistance is defined as *the natural and heritable ability of certain individuals within a weed population to survive the herbicide dose normally used to control them* (HRAC). In every weed population, there is a limited number of plants capable of surviving herbicide treatment.

It is rare for a weed population to be resistant only to the selected herbicide. More often, it is also resistant to other herbicides with the same mode or mechanism of action (MoA), even if it has never been exposed to them. This phenomenon is called *cross-resistance*. In the most severe and difficult-to-manage cases, a resistant population can survive herbicides with different modes of action; this situation is referred to as *multiple resistance*.

In Italy, GIRE (Italian Herbicide Resistance Group - <http://gire.mlib.cnr.it/index.php>) maps resistance phenomena across the country and provides updated databases for weed species and crop types.

Weed management is one of the most critical aspects of agriculture. Each year, significant yield losses are estimated worldwide due to the negative impact of weeds on crop production, both in quantitative and qualitative terms. Chemical control in the form of herbicides has so far represented the most effective tool for weed management.

Regulation (EC) No. 1107/2009 — placing of plant protection products on the market in the European Union — establishes the rules for the authorization, sale, use, and control of these products. Recognizing the precautionary principle, it has reduced the number of herbicides available on the market. This has led to the repeated use of a narrow range of plant protection products with the same mechanism of action, thereby promoting the development of herbicide-resistant weed populations.

Resistance is therefore an evolutionary phenomenon, which requires the use of different herbicides or alternative control methods that may be more costly and/or less effective. Moreover, resistance can persist for several years even in the absence of the selecting herbicide, due to the presence of a seed bank in the soil. In addition, the artificial selection of agronomic traits in crops

beneficial to humans has unintentionally promoted the evolution of weed biotypes resembling cultivated plants (aka, Vavilovian mimicry).

There are currently 537 unique cases (species x site of action) of herbicide resistant weeds globally, with 273 species (156 dicots and 117 monocots). Weeds have evolved resistance to 21 of the 31 known herbicide sites of action and to 168 different herbicides. Herbicide resistant weeds have been reported in 102 crops in 75 countries (International Herbicide-Resistant Weed Database - <https://www.weedscience.org/Home.aspx>). Once resistance becomes frequent within a population, it may rapidly spread to other populations through pollen or seed and may even be transferred to other species through hybridization. An increase in the frequency of application of a particular herbicide is likely to be accompanied by a proportional increase in resistance to that herbicide. Thus, resistance is a highly complex phenomenon resulting from the synergy of multiple factors, both genetic and non-genetic.

Herbicide resistance can be classified into two main categories: target-site resistance (TSR) and non-target-site resistance (NTSR). TSR is caused by DNA mutations that prevent the herbicide from binding to its site of action, thereby nullifying its toxic effect (Figure 2).

Figure 2: TSR scheme

Otherwise, NTSR resistance involves multiple physiological processes that can lead to reduced herbicide uptake, herbicide isolation, and/or enhanced detoxification (Figure 3). In particular, the onset of NTSR through enhanced detoxification is considered of particular importance because

it can confer unpredictable resistance to multiple MoA herbicides, including chemicals never before used to control weeds.

Figure 3: NTSR scheme

NTSRs are often regulated by epigenetic mechanisms (i.e. miRNAs). These resistance phenomena involve epigenetic regulation of the metabolic process of detoxifying the organism from the herbicide (herbicide degradation and/or isolation), which leads to the occurrence of resistance. If triggered by the herbicide administration, epigenetic mechanisms would regulate the organism's gene expression, inducing susceptibility or resistance depending on the type of regulation (stimulation or repression) of the enzymes involved in the detoxification of the plant from the herbicide (i.e. cytochromes, glutathione S-transferase, etc...).

Figure 4: example of epigenetic regulation of enzyme involved in herbicide resistance by miRNAs

Within the Flagship Project VINO, in the Research Module 5 “Innovative technologies for vineyards protection and management in Agriculture 4.0 framework, task 5.5 Sustainable management of herbicide resistance in weeds: identification of different types of herbicide resistance using genetic and omics-based approach”, a survey of the status of the herbicide resistance occurrence in the vineyards of Oltrepo Pavese has been conducted.

Four weed species have been identified as potentially dangerous due to their ability to develop resistance to glyphosate administration in the vineyards: *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) P. Beauv., *Sorghum halepense* (L.) Pers., *Conyza canadensis* Cronq. and *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers.

The survey demonstrated also that the cases of resistance identified were associated with a microRNA-mediated post-transcriptional regulation of enzymes involved in glyphosate detoxification (i.e. ATP-binding cassette (ABC) transporter, aldo-keto reductasi (AKR), cationic aminoacidic transporter (CAT) and cytochromes P450 (CYP450). Hence, all resistant cases could be classified as microRNA-mediated NTSR phenomena.

Moreover, the analysis revealed that resistant biotypes of these weeds were associated with distinct soil microbial profiles in vineyards, which differed from those observed in fields hosting susceptible biotypes.

In light of these findings and given that epigenetic mechanisms are shaped by ecological factors, understanding the ecological context, in particular soil physicochemical properties and microbial composition and biodiversity, represents a crucial step for predicting the potential occurrence of resistance and for guiding the development of targeted, sustainable control strategies.

B) Guidelines for the Management, Prevention, and Containment of Resistance

Factors Related to the Development of Herbicide Resistance

Among the main causes of the development of herbicide-resistant weed populations are:

- repeated use of groups of herbicides with the same mechanism of action (MoA)
- use of herbicides with a very specific site of action against weeds
- number of weed generations
- monocropping
- timing of herbicide applications
- herbicide dosage
- poor functioning of herbicide application equipment
- presence of resistant weeds in the soil seed bank
- ecological factors (stress) that trigger epigenetic adaptive responses in plants.

Actions to Reduce the Occurrence of Herbicide Resistance

To manage herbicide resistance with a more targeted and sustainable approach, the following measures should be taken:

- a regular monitoring of crops and assessment of the effects of herbicide treatments
- to use herbicides more consciously
- alternate the herbicide MoAs used as far as possible
- implement crop rotation practices
- prevent the build-up of the weed seedbank
- implement weed control using alternative methods (e.g., mowing, grazing, etc.).
- apply appropriate agronomic management techniques, including tillage
- preserve and increase microbial biodiversity in the soil using bio stimulants and cover crops
- promote the use of natural products (organic fertilizers, etc.)
- the use of crop varieties that allow for an increase in the number of active substances used, as they are tolerant.

Figure 5: Actions that promote the biodiversity of the microbial soil community, an important factor in reducing the incidence of herbicide resistance

C) Self-Assessment Checklist

Below is a checklist that farmers can use to assess their knowledge about herbicide resistance and their ability to manage the problem. For each question, there are three options to choose from (a, b, c). At the end of the questionnaire, there is an evaluation grid that assigns a score to each answer. The sum of the scores provides an assessment of the risk of resistant weeds being present.

1. Scouting of your fields to verify the effectiveness of herbicide applications. How do you typically do this?

- a. Walk the perimeter of your fields looking for weeds. You notice an irregular patch of weeds and mark the area. Treat them before they go to seed;
- b. Conduct a thorough field survey, stopping to closely inspect selected spots. You are confident in the herbicide application. A patch of weeds catches your eye, but it is likely an area that was missed during the herbicide application;
- c. After a certain number of days, carry out an inspection to check for weeds that are not susceptible to the treatment and note the area to map the farm.

2. Last year, you noticed the presence of viable weeds following treatment. How do you normally proceed?

- a. You believe the presence of weeds is probably due to poor herbicide efficacy or extremely high weed pressure;
- b. Plant a different crop and use a herbicide with a different mode of action;
- c. Continue with your crop plan and monitor and record whether the presence of viable weeds increases after treatment.

3. Herbicide rotation is a way to be proactive in counteracting herbicide resistance. This year, you are determined to:

- a. Try different herbicides to control weeds;
- b. Continue using the same strategies that have worked well so far;
- c. Use a product blend that combines two groups of herbicides that control the same weed.

4. During harvesting:

- a. Clean the combine harvester thoroughly when moving from one field to another;
- b. Clean the combine harvester only if you see a significant viable infestation to

- reduce the risk of spreading weed seeds that may be resistant;
- c. Don't clean the combine harvester at all, considering it a waste of time.

5. After reading an article in a trade journal that highlights the risk of spreading herbicide resistance and recommends good practices, you:

- a. decide to try some of these recommendations;
- b. continue with your normal routine, which seems more economical;
- c. extend these practices across the entire farm.

6. You followed the herbicide dosages recommended on the label but notice that in some areas the weeds have been unaffected by the treatment. You decide to:

- a. collect a weed sample and test it for resistance;
- b. call the herbicide manufacturer and complain about damage, as the herbicide has always worked well;
- c. take alternative measures, including physical means, to eliminate the weeds before they go to seed.

Scoring

Scoring	scores		
Question	A	B	C
1	3	5	0
2	5	3	0
3	4	0	1
4	0	3	5
5	3	5	0
6	0	5	2

Please, sum up the scores you obtained answering each question and check the obtained score with the following grid

Grid for assessing the risk of the presence of resistant weeds

Risk	Score
low	0-10
medium	11-20
high	21-29